

**ANA MIRANDA'S HISTORIOGRAPHIC METAFICTION: A READING
OF THE BIOGRAPHICAL-FICTIONAL NARRATIVES BOCA DO
INFERNO AND DAYS & DAYS**

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ABSTRACT

This project whose title is THE HISTORIOGRAPHIC METAFICTION OF ANA MIRANDA: A READING OF THE BIOGRAPHIC-FICTIONAL NARRATIVES BOCA DO INFERNO AND DIAS & DIAS is part of a broader project carried out in the Portuguese Language Literature Studies Group – GELLP, at the University State of Piauí, Campus professor Barros Araújo, which seeks to investigate the literature of the Portuguese language. It is intended to work the biographical-fictional narratives Boca do Inferno (2006) and Dias & Dias (2002), by Ana Miranda under the aspect of Historiographical Metafiction, supported by the studies of Linda Hutcheon (1991), Poetics of Post-Modernism . It seeks to contribute to the advancement of this area of knowledge, with the expansion of its comparative studies of contemporary Brazilian literature. By proposing a reading of Ana Miranda's works, one perceives the relevance of the theoretical approach to the concepts of fiction and metafiction and, in this context, that of Historiographical Metafiction. Reflections around such concepts become crucial when literary analysis turns to fictional narratives that appropriate history to compose the fictional structure. Ana Miranda, in a set of narratives, develops this aesthetic condition, proposing recreations of historical times and storytelling of the lives of characters that have historical references. In contemporary narratives, in which Miranda's works are framed, the use of historical themes has become frequent, or rather, the re-reading of history in a movement of creation and updating; self-reflection is also a crucial characteristic of these narratives. To carry out the research, we relied on scholars such as Hutcheon (1991), Esteves (1998) and Malard (2010).

Keywords: Historiographic metafiction. Biographical-fictional narratives. Ana Miranda.

1. INTRODUCTION

This project, whose title is THE HISTORIOGRAPHIC METAFICTION OF ANA MIRANDA: A READING OF THE BIOGRAPHICAL-FICTIONAL NARRATIVES BOCA DO INFERNO AND DIAS & DIAS, is part of a broader project carried out at the Study Group on Portuguese Language Literatures – GELLP, at the State University of Piauí, Campus professor Barros Araújo, who seeks to investigate Portuguese language literature. It aims to work on the biographical-fictional narratives Boca do Inferno and Dias & Dias, by Ana Miranda under the aspect of historiographical metafiction. The aim is to contribute to the advancement of this area of knowledge, with the expansion of comparative studies of contemporary Brazilian literature.

When proposing a reading of Ana Miranda's works, one can see the relevance of the theoretical approach to the concepts of fiction and metafiction and, in this context, that of historiographical metafiction. Reflections around such concepts become crucial when literary analysis turns to fictional narratives that appropriate history to compose the fictional structure. Ana Miranda, in a set of narratives, develops this aesthetic condition, proposing recreations of historical times and fables of the lives of characters that have historical referents.

In contemporary narratives, which include Miranda's works, the use of historical themes has become frequent, or rather, the re-reading of history in a movement of creation and updating; Self-reflection is also a crucial characteristic of these narratives. Literary creation has been the focus of fiction itself, as a theme that explores and reflects the process of fictional writing.

2 THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Among the main characteristics of metafiction for understanding texts belonging to the genre; therefore, for reading the historiographical metafictional novels by Ana Miranda and, in particular, Boca do Inferno and Dias & Dias. Firstly, metafiction often employs intertextual references, which allow it to examine fictional systems, incorporate aspects present in theory and literary criticism, create biographies of imaginary writers as well as present and discuss fictional works by an imaginary character. In his deconstructions of the narrative, we find the

author's comments in the text, direct questions to the reader, the author's involvement with fictional characters, in addition to the rejection of a conventional plot. Finally, the presence of self-reflexivity, which allows the texts in question to think about their organization and function. In this context, many of the metafictional characteristics shape Ana Miranda's narratives, and especially in Clarice it is possible to point out the presence of intertextuality and the creation of an imaginary biography, among other reading possibilities.

Inserted in a certain way in metafiction, historiographic metafiction, due to this condition, brings with it metafictional characteristics; however, they are accompanied by a concern of a historiographical nature. Thus, the genre has simultaneously studied theoretical self-awareness and the recognition of history and literature as human constructions, for a study and approach to literary forms and historical content. Exactly as Linda Hutcheon points out, when thinking about the aesthetics of postmodern discourse, it is "historical and metafictional, contextual and self-reflective, always aware of its status as a discourse, of human elaboration" (HUTCHEON, 1991, p. 79). Thus, it is in historiographic metafiction that both discourses, the literary and the historical, are tensioned, since the boundaries between fiction and history are increasingly blurred and less clear (SILVA, 2006).

The research corpus analyzes the two works *Boca do Inferno* (1989) and *Dias & Dias* (2002), by Ana Miranda. The first is narrated in third person, divided into chapters: *The City, The Crime, The Revenge, The Wanton, The Fall and The Destiny* (epilogue). The second has ten chapters: *The voluptuousness of saudade, A thrush in the cage, Fictions of the ideal, The Balaiada, The levian mimosa, Camels in Ceará, The irrational always wins, Angel with clipped wings, A storm on the horizon and Epilogue*.

The first historical novel mentioned began to be written in 1979, but was only published ten years later, as a result of much research and reading, it became a bestseller and was translated in several countries. The narrative is presented in Bahia during the 17th century, where it references historical and literary characters from this period, such as Antônio de Souza de Menezes, who was nicknamed *Braço de Prata*, who used a piece of metal in place of his arm, which was lost in a naval battle against Dutch invaders, the Jesuit Padre Antônio Viera and the poet Gregório de Matos nicknamed *Boca do Inferno*, the central character of the novel, who criticizes the Bahian colonial society that was marked by corruption, debauchery and the struggle for power. The narrative begins like this:

The city was built on the inner southern extremity of the peninsula, at thirteen degrees south latitude and forty-two degrees west longitude, on the coast of Brazil. It was in front of a wide and clean cove that gave it its name: Bahia...In

a gentle A region crossed by clear rivers, with an always blue sky, fertile land, forests of leafy trees, the city seemed to be the image of Paradise. It was, however, where demons enticed souls to populate Hell (MIRANDA, 1989, p. 12).

To analyze the process of historiographic metafiction in Boca do Inferno and Dias & Dias, theories such as those of the author Hutcheon (1991) were sought, analyzing the discursive path within the novels, and their process of transporting the historical essence within the narrated plot.

Historiographical metafiction refutes natural, or common sense, methods for distinguishing between historical fact and fiction. She refuses the view that only history has a claim to truth, by questioning the basis of this claim in historiography and by asserting that both history and fiction are discourses, human constructs, systems of meaning, and are It is from this identity that the two obtain their main claim to truth. This type of postmodern fiction also refuses the relegation of the extratextual past to the domain of historiography in the name of the autonomy of art (HUTCHEON, 1991, p. 127).

When we start reading Dias & Dias, we are introduced to the fictional character Feliciano, who will lead the entire narrative of the plot, narrating the platonic love she had for Antônio Gonçalves Dias. The plot starts from the characters' childhood in Caixas no Maranhão, where Feliciano believes that Antônio had written a poem dedicated to her.

I carry in my hands the verses that Antônio wrote for my green eyes, how old were we? I was twelve, and he was thirteen, because this happened in 1836. The poem talks about green eyes, and at that moment, when I read it for the first time, I believed they were my eyes, but my eyes are not actually green, they are more the color of the almost dry palm leaf, or perhaps the color of the water in the bay of São Marcos, a water dirty with mud and sand moving shallows, disturbed by the dimensions of the moon, by the incessant passage of the fishing sloops, this water that I now see in the distance morning sun (MIRANDA, 2002, p. 15).

The poet's life becomes known to the character through letters he sends to his friend Alexandre Teófilo. Shown to Feliciano by Maria Luiza, Alexandre's wife, the letters report several events experienced by the poet. These letters create an illusion of reality in the novel, which make the reader forget the fictionality of Feliciano and the other characters, placing them in the same sphere of existence as Gonçalves Dias and Alexandre Teófilo.

The novel portrays the 19th century, where the Balaiada revolt that occurred in the interior of the province in Maranhão between 1838 and 1841 is highlighted, caused by popular dissatisfaction where cowboys, slaves and other disadvantaged people fought for better living conditions and protested against political abuses. of the large farmers, resulting in the conquest of a provisional government that placed the Portuguese out of the city of Caxias.

And it was then that another revolt came in Caxias, in the year 38, or 39, I believe, a popular rebellion, an insurrection of hate, vicious rascals, led by the cowboy Cara Preta, and Balaio, and the black Cosme who had been slave. It all started in Vila da Manga, not in Caxias, to deny those who say they are the people from Caxias more insurgent than the Portuguese (MIRANDA, 2002, p. 107).

Likewise, the author adds Feliciano's conception of this event. These elements mix and cause the fictional historical effect that we are addressing.

The poor people of Balaiada, with the help of many residents, like my father, dominated the region, there was a rush, shooting everywhere, now here, now there, the poor took over the houses of important people who fled from their farms to others, they burned them down houses of farmers, the richest, created a "provisional government" for Brazil, [...] I liked the baskets, the poor, I felt sorry for the slaves and the Indians, but I also felt sorry for the Portuguese, I thought of João Manuel, he had been a good man, he would not deserve such suffering, humiliation once again, [...]. (MIRANDA, 2002, p. 109)

It is worth highlighting that Ana Miranda has, throughout her literary production, dialogued with the poetics of contemporary narratives, demonstrating great capacity in reinventing history and the history of literature itself, articulating, in some of her works, literary themes. Through the highlighted works, the author reinvents the literary universe, dialogues with history and literature, both presented intertextually, and creates imagined life stories, making historical subjects, such as Gregório de Matos Guerra and Gonçalves Dias, characters from her fiction. . With the creation of such works, Miranda shows herself to be a reader of national literature, being able to move between the literary texts read, creating from reading.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We believe that this project will help to form more attentive, observant and critical readers, in addition to encouraging undergraduate students to get involved with literature. We seek to improve and continue the studies of the GELLP - Group of Studies and Research in Portuguese Language Literatures, at the State University of Piauí, professor Barros Araújo campus.

By continuously and assiduously reading this book, it will be possible to fully understand this work, which is highlighted as complex by many readers. And with the constant search for knowledge related to historiographic metafiction, it will be possible to master all its characteristics in the explored narrative and also in other Brazilian works.

It is expected, through the methodological procedures described, to clarify the concept of historiographic metafiction and the possible relationships between the biographical-fictional narratives of the Ceará writer Ana Miranda. Finally, the aim is to revisit the past from a perspective different from the official historical discourse and the parodic use of intertext as a constitutive element of the novel.

4 CONCLUSION

In view of the theoretical positions, it is worth highlighting that Ana Miranda has, throughout her literary production, dialogued with the poetics of contemporary narratives, demonstrating great capacity in reinventing history and the history of literature itself, articulating, in some of her works, themes literary. Thus, the history of literature gains space and is reread in three of the author's novels, *Boca do Inferno*, *The Last Quimera* and *Dias & Dias*, and in the novel *Clarice*. Through the highlighted works, the author reinvents the literary universe, dialogues with history and literature, both placed intertextually, and creates imagined life stories, playing historical subjects, such as Gregório de Matos Guerra, Augusto dos Anjos, Gonçalves Dias and Clarice Lispector, characters from her fiction. With the creation of such works, Miranda shows herself to be a reader of national literature, being able to move between the literary texts read, creating from reading.

By reading Ana Miranda's works, we will seek to follow a common path between *Boca do Inferno* and *Dias & Dias*, precisely with regard to the fictionalization of lives and the re-reading of literary history.

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